

Agroforestry and Fodder Integration: A Sustainable Strategy for Peri-Urban Dairy Production in Punjab, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

This study aimed to identify the ongoing feeding practices and nutritional strategies in Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal districts. Data collection involved face-to-face interviews with farmers directly involved in dairy farm operations. A total of 100 respondents (50 from each district) were interviewed using a semi-structured pretested questionnaire. The snowball sampling technique was used to collect data from two types of dairy farms characterized as semi-commercial (SCOM) and commercial (COM) based on the number of dairy animals. Keeping in view the objective of this study, data were collected related to demographic information, location, herd size, milk production, nutritional strategies, feeding practices, types of feed used (green fodder, dry fodder, silage, concentrate, supplements), seasonal variations in feed availability, nutritional management, feed adjustments based on availability, feeding adjustments based on milk yield and lactation stage, environmental considerations, and overall husbandry/management practices. Collected data were tabulated, coded, and statistically analyzed. Results showed that 60% of respondents were farm owners, and 47% had 6-10 years of experience in dairy farming. Knowledge regarding feeding practices was found to be high in 69% of the farmers, while 23% had average knowledge. Modern shed designs were observed on 67% of the farms. Silage was the primary feed used by 67% of farmers, while 33% relied on green fodder, including maize, sorghum, berseem, and alfalfa. Additionally, 91% of respondents prepared their own dry fodder, and 81% prepared homemade silage. Concentrate usage was dominated by commercial mixes (70%), followed by homemade concentrates (20%), cottonseed cake (7%), and wheat bran (3%). A small number (18%) of semi-commercial farms grazed their animals daily, while animals on commercial farms were not allowed to graze. Group feeding was practiced by 75% of farmers, primarily based on production levels (58%). Crop residues were commonly used by 99% of respondents. Feed cost was the major challenge faced by 79% of the farmers, while 21% cited labor costs. Statistically significant differences ($P \leq 0.001$) were observed in farm area and daily milk production between the two farm types, with commercial farms yielding higher production (100 ± 3.29 liters) than semi-commercial farms (18 ± 1.29 liters). The number of workers was significantly different ($P \leq 0.005$) between the two farm types.

Keywords: Feeding practices, nutritional strategies, sustainable dairy production, grazing, commercial farms, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

The dairy industry is a substantial provider to the overall food system, providing necessary nutrients and livelihoods for millions of people worldwide (FAO, 2013). One of the key factors influencing the sustainability of dairy production is the feeding practices used on dairy farms (Knaus, 2015). Nonetheless, the sector is faced with a few limitations, such as a weak supply of nutritious feed, inadequate nutrition control, and small-scale agricultural activities, which impede the future and sustainability of the industry (Tariq et al., 2021). Feeding practices applied in semi-commercial and commercial dairy farms should be evaluated to determine areas that need improvement towards more sustainable dairy production (Gerber et al., 2013). This can be accomplished in relation to the type of feed and feed quantity, as well as farm feeding management practices (Knaus, 2015). Understanding the feeding practices of semi-commercial and commercial dairy producers may assist in identifying entry points for more focused measures to improve sustainability by encouraging the uptake of nutrient administration planning. For example, farmers can be encouraged to adopt efficient feeding systems and locally accessible feed mats, which they can implement in their businesses (Weiss & Wyatt, 2000).

Commercial feeding methods of animals also influence their productivity and the nutritional status of dairy animals (NRC, 2001). Mertens et al. (2009) indicate that dairy farmers ought to separate feeding parameters that incorporate variables such as intake quantities, rate, and frequency. In addition, the performance and quality (Allen et al., 2017) of animals and the observation of feed to offer an optimal amount of nutrition and production are necessary. One of the major factors that determine dairy production in Pakistan is the conventional feeding practices used by dairy farmers (Iqbal et al., 2018). Since feeding patterns have the potential to influence animal health, milk production, and the sustainability of the environment, their assessment is essential to improve such processes to ensure sustainable dairy production (Khan et al., 2020). Conventional feeding is often applied by dairy producers in Pakistan, and it involves commercial feeds and concentrates, dry roughages, and green fodder (Ahmed et al., 2019). The practice of using available and locally sourced feeds and forages, as well as more sophisticated scientific feeding methods at the least economic cost, is one of the most significant ways of ensuring sustainable production of dairy products (Hussain et al., 2019). Proper livestock rotational grazing systems and improved housing to minimize heat stress have been identified as means to increase dairy resilience in a scenario where fodder is scarce in the global food system (Younus et al., 2024; Correia et al., 2021).

The purpose of this study is to assess the feasibility of integrating fodder and agroforestry as sustainable strategies for peri-urban dairy production in Punjab, Pakistan. This research involves a baseline survey conducted in two major dairy-producing districts, Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal, focusing on the feeding practices and nutritional strategies employed by semi-commercial and commercial farms to promote sustainable dairy production. The findings will provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers and dairy farmers, supporting the adoption of commercially viable and climate-resilient production models to ensure the long-term sustainability of the peri-urban dairy industry in the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Site

This research was conducted in two districts of Punjab province, Pakistan, which are renowned as significant contributors to the dairy industry of this nation: Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal. Toba Tek Singh has become a powerhouse in dairying in the country and is also a renowned milk-producing pocket in the province, boasting a booming dairy industry. The commercial dairy farms not only meet the district's needs but also supply other regions. Toba Tek Singh, with its massive capacity in semi-commercial and commercial farms and developed infrastructure, can continue to lead dairy production in Pakistan. Sahiwal is a prominent producer of milk in Pakistan due to the immense number of dairy cows native to Sahiwal in the peri-urban areas. With its famous Sahiwal breed of cattle, the region will be vital in the supply chain of dairy production, thanks to its numerous smallholder and commercial dairy farms, which are known for their high milk yields and adaptability.

Figure: 1 GPS Map and Visual Representation of Sampling Stations Sited in Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal Districts

Study Design and Sampling

A cross-sectional survey was conducted using a snowball sampling technique. A total of 100 dairy farms were categorized into two types based on herd size and milk production levels:

- Semi-commercial (SCOM; n = 50)
- Commercial (COM; n = 50)

Data were collected using a semi-structured, pre-tested questionnaire and on-site farm observations as shown in figure: 1.

Measured Variables

In addition to statistical criteria, selection was guided by expert judgment and theoretical relevance based on prior research and field knowledge, ensuring that key variables with practical implications for feeding practices were retained. Those variables included farm type, herd size, number of milking animals, feed sources, feed quality adjustment, feeding system, feeding frequency, mineral supplementation, silage usage, silage feeding strategy, non-conventional feed use, adoption of alternative fodder crops, and management strategies.

Table: 1 List of variables and description

Variable Group	Measured Variable	Definition / Measurement Description
Demographics	Farm Type	Semi-commercial, Commercial
	Herd Size	Total number of animals per farm
Feeding Practices	Feed Sources	Green fodder, silage, concentrates, wheat straw, crop residues
	Feed Quantity Adjustment	Based on milk yield, fixed quantity, or traditional knowledge
	Feeding System	Individual feeding or group feeding
	Feeding Frequency	Number of feeding times per day (e.g., once, twice, thrice)
Nutritional Strategies	Concentrate Type	Commercial, homemade, or mixed
	Mineral Supplementation	Type and frequency of mineral use (e.g., salt blocks, powder, liquids)
	Water Availability	Source and regularity of drinking water for animals
Feed Resource Status	Green Fodder Source	Home grown or purchased
	Silage Usage	Whether silage is used; frequency and amount per day
	Silage Preparation	Home grown or purchased silage
	Use of Crop Residues	Wheat straw, maize stover, sugarcane tops
Scarcity Management	Scarcity Occurrence	Frequency of fodder scarcity: Regular, Occasional, or Absent
	Scarcity Months	Total months per year when fodder is insufficient
	Coping Strategies	Market purchase, reduced herd size, alternative feeds (e.g., silage, hay, urea-treated straw)
Alternative Resources	Adoption of Alternative Feeds	Silage, hay, treated straw, non-conventional by-products
Economic Impact	Monthly Feed Cost	Average feed expenditure per month (PKR)
	Milk Sale Income	Total revenue from milk sales per month (PKR)

	Revenue Loss Due to Scarcity	Farmer-reported income drop during feed shortage period (%)
Perceptions & Attitudes	Perceived Causes of Scarcity	Drought, seasonal variation, fodder demand, lack of land
	Attitude Toward Sustainability	Whether the farmer perceives their feeding as sustainable

Data Processing and Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics (means, percentages, and frequencies) were used to summarize farm characteristics and feeding practices. Chi-square tests were applied to assess associations between farm types and feeding strategies. Pearson correlation analysis was performed to evaluate relationships between farm scale, silage use, fodder cultivation practices, and fodder scarcity duration. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Dairy Farms

The survey encompassed 100 dairy farms in Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal District, with an equal distribution across Semi-commercial (SCOM), and Commercial (COM) farms (n=50 for each category).

Table: 2 Descriptive statistics of demographic and farm characteristics of the surveyed dairy farms, categorized by farm type (Semi-commercial, and Commercial).

Variables	Farm Types		Overall
	SCOM	COM	
Total Number of Animals at Farm (Mean \pm SD)	26.5 \pm 9.18	72.55 \pm 38.15	57.20 \pm 48.48
Number of Milking Cows	10.38 \pm 3.5	28.43 \pm 11.67	22.41 \pm 19.53
Farm Area (acres)	0.79 \pm 0.75	1.25 \pm 0.53	1.09 \pm 0.75
Experience in Farming	Frequencies (%)		
<6 years	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
6–10 years	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.0%)	2 (1.7%)
11–16 years	5 (12.5%)	23 (28.7%)	28 (23.3%)
>17 years	35 (87.5%)	55 (68.7%)	90 (75.0%)
Respondent's Knowledge of Feeding Practice			
Perfect	2 (5.0%)	38 (47.5%)	40 (33.3%)
Average	38 (95.0%)	40 (50.0%)	78 (65.0%)
No Knowledge	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.5%)	2 (1.7%)
Age of Respondent			
20–30	0 (0.0%)	9 (11.2%)	9 (7.5%)

31–40	12 (30.0%)	20 (25.0%)	32 (26.7%)
41–50	16 (40.0%)	35 (43.7%)	51 (42.5%)
>51	12 (30.0%)	15 (18.7%)	28 (23.3%)
Education Level			
Uneducated	2 (5.0%)	2 (2.5%)	4 (3.3%)
Under Metric	24 (60.0%)	17 (21.2%)	41 (34.2%)
Metric	9 (22.5%)	35 (43.7%)	44 (36.7%)
Inter	4 (10.0%)	14 (17.5%)	18 (15.0%)
Graduated	1 (2.5%)	12 (15.0%)	13 (10.8%)

Farm Size

Regarding farm size, commercial farms exhibited significantly larger scales compared to semi-commercial farms. Commercial farms had an average of 72.55 ± 38.15 total animals and 28.43 ± 11.67 milking cows, with a larger average farm area of 1.25 ± 0.53 acres. In contrast, semi-commercial farms maintained smaller herd sizes and landholdings, with 26.50 ± 9.18 total animals, 10.38 ± 3.52 milking cows, and an average area of 0.79 ± 0.75 acres. These differences reflect the more extensive resources available to commercial operations.

Knowledge and Age of Respondents

Respondents' knowledge of feeding practices varied notably between farm types. A significant proportion of commercial farmers (47.5%) rated their feeding knowledge as 'Perfect', compared to only 5.0% of semi-commercial farmers. Conversely, 95.0% of semi-commercial farmers rated their knowledge as 'Average', compared to 50.0% of commercial farmers. This trend suggests a higher level of technical awareness among commercial farm operators.

The age distribution indicated that the largest group of respondents overall fell within the 41-50 years bracket (42.5%), with 43.7% of commercial farmers and 40.0% of semi-commercial farmers in this range. Younger farmers aged 20-30 years were the least represented, accounting for only 7.5% of the total respondents.

Education Levels and Experience of Respondents

Education levels showed clear contrasts across the two farm types. Among semi-commercial farmers, the most common educational background was 'Under Metric' (60.0%), indicating limited formal education. In contrast, commercial farms showed a more diversified educational profile: 'Metric' (43.7%), 'Inter' (17.5%), and 'Graduated' (15.0%), highlighting a higher educational attainment in commercial systems.

The experience level among farmers was generally high across both farm types. 87.5% of semi-commercial farmers had more than 17 years of experience, while 68.7% of commercial farmers reported the same. Farmers with 11-16 years of experience were more frequently found among commercial farms (28.7%) than in semi-commercial setups (12.5%). These results underline a predominantly experienced farming population, particularly within semi-commercial systems.

Sustainable Dairy Farming

Sustainable dairy farming is characterized by the efficient use of available resources, environmental responsibility, and economic viability. About 87% of the respondents considered their feeding practices sustainable. This perception stemmed from the use of home-grown feeds, silage, and reduced dependence on external inputs. However, actual sustainability indicators such as balanced nutrient supply, seasonal adaptability, and long-term productivity revealed room for improvement. Many farms lacked scientific feeding protocols and proper mineral supplementation, both of which are essential for true sustainability.

Feeding Management

Feeding management among the surveyed farms was largely informal. About 63% of farmers adjusted feed quantities based on milk yield, while the rest followed fixed or experience-based rations. Group feeding was observed in 75% of farms, primarily aimed at reducing labor and feed wastage. Individual animal feeding, which can enhance efficiency, was rare due to high labor demands. Furthermore, mineral supplementation was inconsistent and mostly limited to common salt blocks without structured nutrient planning.

Generalize Feeding

Most farms practiced generalized feeding, relying on traditional knowledge and visual cues like animal body condition or milk output. Only 10-15% of farmers used tools such as weight scales, milk meters, or lab testing for feed evaluation. This non-scientific approach led to either underfeeding or overfeeding, both of which can reduce productivity and increase costs.

Feed Types

The main feed type includes; silage, green fodder, wheat straw, and concentrates etc.

Table 3: Average Feed Intake per Animal per Day

Parameter	Average Value
Silage Intake (kg/day)	26.16
Green Fodder Intake (kg/day)	18.35
Wheat Straw Intake (kg/day)	2.69
Concentrate Intake (kg/day)	7.12
Dry Matter Intake (kg/day)	18.32

Figure: 2 Average Feed Intakes per Animal per Day

These feeds were often offered in combination, although most farmers lacked awareness about crude protein (CP) or total digestible nutrient (TDN) content, leading to imbalanced rations (Table 3 and figure 2).

Green Fodder (Home Grown/Purchased)

About 85% of farmers used green fodder as a primary feed source. Of these, 70% grew fodder on their own farms, including crops like berseem, maize, sorghum, millet, and lucerne. The remaining 30% purchased green fodder from neighboring farmers or local markets. Fodder availability was highly seasonal, and during scarcity periods, farmers shifted toward dry matter sources or commercial feeds.

Roughages (Home Grown/Purchased)

Wheat straw was the main roughage used across farms, obtained either from their own crop residues or purchased during harvest season. About 75% of farms relied on home-produced roughages, while the rest used market-purchased straw. Techniques like urea treatment of straw, which could enhance nutritional quality, were very rarely adopted due to lack of awareness and training.

Concentrates (Homemade/Commercial)

Concentrate feeding was a common practice to boost milk production, a large number 70% used commercial concentrate feeds from local or branded suppliers, 20% formulated concentrates at home, using ingredients like cottonseed cake, canola meal, wheat bran, and maize grains and 10% used a combination of homemade and commercial sources. Though commercial feeds were appreciated for ease of use, some

farmers expressed concerns about cost, variability in quality, and potential adulteration.

Scarcity Period Management

Two main feed scarcity periods were reported: Summer (May to July) and winter (December to January). During these months, green fodder production was low due to climatic constraints. Farmers responded by increasing use of silage and hay, relying more on concentrates, Reducing herd size or limiting feed intake However, only 22% of farms had forward planning strategies like preserving fodder or preparing silage well in advance.

Alternative Feed Resources (Silage, Hay, Urea Treatment)

Silage was adopted by 82% of farms, with 93% preparing it themselves using maize or sorghum. This helped ensure feed availability during lean seasons. Hay was used by 18% of farmers, often made from surplus berseem or seasonal grasses. Urea-treated straw technique was used by only 6% of farms, mostly among better-informed or semi-commercial setups. Knowledge and labor intensity were barriers to wider adoption.

Agriculture or Crop Residues

Crop residues like wheat straw, rice husk, maize stover, and sugarcane tops were widely used 78% of farms incorporated these into rations. Although easily available and low-cost, their nutritional value was poor and often led to reduced digestibility. Very few farmers practiced molasses enrichment or urea treatment to improve the feed quality.

Grazing and Grazing Land

Grazing was uncommon in commercial setups due to land scarcity. Only 18% of farmers, typically semi-commercial ones in rural outskirts or villages, allowed animals to graze part-time. Grazing lands were usually communal or temporarily allocated fallow fields. Seasonal grazing during monsoon or spring was beneficial, but pasture management practices were absent, limiting its nutritional contribution.

Feed Composition in Dairy Farms

A pie chart below represents the average feed composition in the surveyed dairy farms; silage and green fodder collectively form a major part of the daily feed, followed by concentrates, wheat straw, and other supplementary resources (Figure 3).

Figure: 3 Proportional Feed Composition in Semi-commercial and Commercial Farms

Important Factors of Dairy Production in Punjab

The key factors influencing dairy production in Punjab includes feed availability and feeding practices, grazing, access to clean water, veterinary support and extension services, milk market pricing, farmer awareness and training, labor and landholding size farms that maintained consistent feeding schedules, used balanced rations, and had access to technical support showed better performance in terms of milk yield and economic returns.

Group Comparison Analysis Based on Farm Type

The heat map represents the correlation coefficients between different practices in dairy farms. The color scale ranges from blue (strong positive correlation) to red (strong negative correlation), with white representing a weak or no correlation. The numerical values on the map are correlation coefficients, indicating strength and direction of the relationship (Figure 4).

Figure: 4 Group Comparison Analysis Based on Farm Type

DISCUSSION

Importance Dairy Farming in Pakistan

The present study, conducted across two major dairy-producing districts Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal aimed to evaluate feeding practices and nutritional strategies adopted by semi-commercial and commercial farms to ensure sustainable dairy production.

Demographic Characteristics

There was an equal number of semi-commercial and commercial setups of the farms, which made it possible to compare them in a controlled way. Descriptive statistics indicated that a large variation ($p < 0.05$) was found in the various parameters in terms of total daily milk production, silage utilization, levels of feed input, and monthly income. These results support the earlier conclusions from Tariq et al. (2021) that commercial farms were more resource-efficient and profitable because of superior feeding approaches and management control. Some of the key variables in this study were age and experience, as the respondents had between 6 and 10 years of experience, whereas 37% were aged between 31 and 40 years as shown in table: 2. These results indicate a medium age and a population with a reasonably sizable and experienced agricultural society. According to the findings by Quddus et al. (2018) and Singh et al. (2018), their farm management behavior in this age category allows them to be more receptive to innovations and less hesitant to adopt the suggested technologies. The educational level of the respondents is very high, with 42 percent of them completing their intermediate education and 35 percent completing their

graduation as shown in table: 2. A similar finding was made in Sharma et al. (2019) and Triveni et al. (2018), who found that educated farmers were more oriented toward using best practices, i.e., using concentrates, mineral supplementation, and ration balancing.

Feeding Practices Sustainable Dairy Production

The silage (67%) was a dominant primary feed, with top figures (2-4) reported after green fodder (33%). This is consistent with the observations by Saglıcak et al. (2021), who noted that higher usage of silage is an indicator of modernization in the dairying feeding systems. Furthermore, the widespread use of homemade silage (93.1%) reflects local adaptability and cost-conscious strategies as shown in table: 1. Dry fodder was predominantly sourced through on-farm production (92.9%), highlighting a level of self-sufficiency in roughage provision. However, feed analysis practices were underutilized, with 40% of farmers not conducting any feed testing. This lack of nutrient profiling can result in underfeeding or overfeeding, both of which impact farm economics and milk yield. Most respondents (64%) fed animals twice a day, while 33% did so three times daily, demonstrating an improvement from the traditional once-a-day feeding still seen in some regions. Concentrates were identified as the primary feed stimulus for milk letdown by 78% of the respondents, which aligns with the established role of energy and protein-rich feeds in lactation physiology (Gerber et al., 2013). The widespread use of commercial concentrate mixes (70%) and the inclusion of homemade rations (20%) further demonstrate the progression toward modern feeding regimes. There are broadly similar trends also reported for Kenya and Tanzania, which favored commercial feeds over local feeds for consistency of quality and nutrient density (Njarui et al., 2011; Maleko et al., 2018).

Use of Crop Residues and Local Feed Resources

An encouraging 99% of farmers incorporated crop residues into their feeding systems. This aligns with sustainable practices emphasized by Sarwar et al. (2002) and Musa et al. (2020), where the utilization of agro-industrial by-products enhances feed resource efficiency. Incorporation of wheat straw, sugarcane tops, and cotton residues not only reduces feeding costs but also minimizes environmental waste.

Grazing

Dairy animals are allowed to graze the fields in many areas of Pakistan. Grazing is a limited but relevant feeding practice in Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal, with only 18% of semi-commercial farms utilizing it, while commercial farms did not use grazing at all. This decline reflects shifting trends toward stall-feeding due to urbanization and land scarcity. Where practiced, grazing helps reduce feed costs and improve nutrient diversity during fodder shortages (Khan et al., 2020; Sarwar et al., 2002). As noted by Beigh et al. (2020), managed grazing can enhance sustainability by lowering reliance on purchased feed.

Role of Grazing in Sustainable Dairy Production

Grazing remains the primary and economically viable nutrition option to semi-commercial dairy farmers, rural (and peri-urban) in particular. It speaks straight at the

largest cost in dairy farms feeding costs by letting animals forage natural pastures. Dairy animals It is important to note that milk can be produced in bovines. In most regions of Pakistan, they were permitted to graze the fields. In Pakistan, fodder shortage takes place on harsh winter (Dec-January) and harsh summer (May-to-July) months (Tariq et al., 2021). The fast urbanization causes land rivalry which limits the grazing areas throughout the land. Regions where dairy farming is practiced where a properly managed grazing system serves as an economic cushion, it can save a farmer heavily on costly purchased feeds and it can render the whole institution of farming self-sufficient makes the operation more efficient and resistant. Beyond cost savings, grazing provides a major nutritional advantage. Pastures are a natural source of diverse forage, including various grasses, legumes, and forbs that offer a more complete and balanced diet than a standard, purchased feed mix. This nutritional diversity is vital for promoting better herd health, improving immune systems, and enhancing animal welfare by allowing for natural foraging behaviors. Therefore, animals that graze regularly are often healthier and productive, leading to higher milk yields and better quality milk.

To maximize these benefits, farmers must appliance a managed grazing system rather than just letting animals roam freely. Techniques such as rotational grazing are crucial. This involves moving the herd between different paddocks to prevent overgrazing, which allows pastures to recover and regrow. A well rotational and managed system ensures a continuous supply of good quality forage all over the grazing season. By integrating this managed grazing with other feeding sources, such as conserved feeds (silage, oats, and hay) and vitamin or mineral supplements, farmers can create a strong and sustainable feeding plan that enhances the economic viability and environmental sustainability of their dairy enterprise.

Nutritional Strategies, Feed Quality Control and Sustainability Perceptions

Feeding quality was generally rated as good to very good by 81% of the respondents, but only 40% of farms regularly analyzed their feed. Among them, feed judgment was primarily based on visual indicators like color (73%) and particle size (25%), with minimal reliance on scientific criteria such as pH (2%). This subjective approach to feed quality evaluation indicates a critical knowledge gap, echoing findings by Maleko et al. (2018) that improper feed assessment hampers milk productivity and feed efficiency.

Sustainability of Feeding Practices

Most respondents (87%) considered their feeding practices sustainable, mainly due to reliance on self-grown fodder (92.9%) and local feed sources. However, only 26% practiced balanced feed formulation, which is essential for true sustainability (Khan et al., 2020). Key improvements suggested were better animal health (42%) and feed availability (28%), aligning with Beigh et al. (2020), Bosire et al. (2019), and Maleko et al. (2018), who emphasized health, feed quality, and nutrient balance as core to sustainable dairy farming.

Feeding Frequency and Stimulus

Most farms (64%) fed animals twice daily, with 33% feeding three times per day. Feeding frequency is positively associated with milk yield and cow health, as highlighted by Beigh et al. (2020). Concentrates were the most common stimulus for milking (78%), underscoring their importance in production stimulation.

Feeding Management for Milking vs. Dry Animals

A majority (83%) of farms practiced differentiated feeding for lactating and dry animals as shown in table: 2. This shows awareness of varying nutritional demands at different physiological stages. Tariq et al. (2021) found similar feeding differentiation in Faisalabad farms, where group feeding based on productivity improved economic outcomes. Likewise, 75% of respondents practiced group feeding, and 78.4% of those based it on production levels further affirming that performance-based nutrition is gaining traction.

Economic Implications of Feeding Choices

Feed was reported as the most significant cost in dairy production by 79% of respondents. This is consistent with global patterns, where feed accounts for 60-70% of dairy production costs (FAO, 2013). Silage-based feeding, though efficient in bulk storage and cost, requires upfront investment in storage facilities and preservation techniques. Homemade silage usage by 81% of farms shows potential for cost-saving, but without technical guidance, risks of nutrient loss and spoilage are high.

CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed feeding practices and nutritional strategies for sustainable dairy production on semi-commercial and commercial farms in Toba Tek Singh and Sahiwal, Punjab. Both farm types showed an increasing use of improved methods like self-prepared silage and group feeding based on productivity. While feeding was adjusted according to lactation stages and milk yield, most farms relied on visual assessments rather than scientific techniques like pH testing or laboratory analysis. Only a few formulated balanced rations, highlighting a gap in technical knowledge despite a high level of confidence among farmers in their systems. Crop residues were commonly used, supporting cost-effective nutrition, though they were rarely treated or enriched. Feed costs remained the highest input, emphasizing the need for efficient, scientifically informed practices. Grazing, though limited, offers numerous benefits, enhancing animal welfare, reducing feed costs, and improving animal health and productivity. When managed well, it supports biodiversity and long-term sustainability. However, land scarcity and seasonal variation are barriers, requiring supplemental feeding and planned pasture rotation. The study concludes that integrating scientific feeding principles, improving farmer education, and supporting practical tools for ration formulation are crucial for advancing sustainability and productivity in Pakistan's dairy sector.

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